

Actively Learning $\mathcal{E}\mathcal{L}$ Terminologies from Large Language Models (Appendix)

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Appendix for the paper “Actively Learning $\mathcal{E}\mathcal{L}$ Terminologies from Large Language Models” accepted at ECAI 2025, main track.

A The algorithm for $\mathcal{E}\mathcal{L}$ terminologies

For the convenience of the reader, here we provide the definitions of the operations performed by the ExactLearner [1]. In the following, we sometimes treat $\mathcal{E}\mathcal{L}$ concepts as tree structures, given that the underlying structure of the concepts is tree-shaped, and speak of ‘nodes’ and ‘successors’ with this correspondence in mind.

Right \mathcal{O} -essential concept inclusion α is computed by applying exhaustively the following rules to $A \sqsubseteq C$:

- Concept saturation for \mathcal{O} : If $\mathcal{O} \models A \sqsubseteq C'$ and C' results from C by adding a concept name A' to the label of some node, then replace $A \sqsubseteq C$ by $A \sqsubseteq C'$.
- Sibling merging for \mathcal{O} : If $\mathcal{O} \models A \sqsubseteq C'$ and C' is the result of identifying in C two r -successors of the same node then replace $A \sqsubseteq C$ by $A \sqsubseteq C'$.
- Decomposition on the right for \mathcal{O} : If d' is an r -successor of d in C , A' is in the node label of d , and $\mathcal{O} \models A' \sqsubseteq \exists r.C_{d'}$, plus $A' \not\sqsubseteq_{\mathcal{O}} A$ if d is the root of C , then replace $A \sqsubseteq C$ by
 - $A' \sqsubseteq \exists r.C_{d'}$ if $\mathcal{H} \not\models A' \sqsubseteq \exists r.C_{d'}$; or
 - $A \sqsubseteq C_{d'\downarrow}$, otherwise, where C_d is the concept corresponding to the subtree rooted in d and $C_{d'\downarrow}$ is the concept corresponding to the result of removing the subtree rooted in d' from C .

Left \mathcal{O} -essential concept inclusion α is computed by exhaustively applying the following rules to $C \sqsubseteq A$.

- Concept saturation for \mathcal{H} : If $\mathcal{H} \models C \sqsubseteq C'$ and C' results from C by adding a concept name A' to the label of some node, then replace $C \sqsubseteq A$ by $C' \sqsubseteq A$.
- Decomposition on the left for \mathcal{O} : If d is a non-root node such that $\mathcal{O} \models C_{d\downarrow} \sqsubseteq A'$ and $\mathcal{H} \not\models C_{d\downarrow} \sqsubseteq A'$, for some $A' \in \text{Nc}(\mathcal{O})$, then replace $C \sqsubseteq A$ by $C_{d\downarrow} \sqsubseteq A'$; if $\mathcal{O} \models C_d \sqsubseteq A'$ and $\mathcal{H} \not\models C_d \sqsubseteq A'$, for some $A' \in \text{Nc}(\mathcal{O})$, then replace $C \sqsubseteq A$ by $C_d \sqsubseteq A'$.

B Individual Learning Performance

We report the remaining results of ExactLearner+LLM for the small ontologies. Table 1 for the Football ontology, Table 2 for the Generations ontology, and finally Table 3 for the University ontology.

Table 1: Individual results of ExactLearner+LLM on the Football ontology. All the results have been analysed with the Chi-Squared test. The null hypothesis is that there is no correlation between the ontology in constructed by ExactLearner+LLM and the Football ontology. A yellow line means that the p-value is greater than 0.05 (i.e., the null hypothesis cannot be refused).

Model	Prompt & Query	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-Score
Llama2 (13b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.239	0.963	0.165	0.282
	Natural Language	0.619	0.89	0.275	0.42
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.325	0.933	0.179	0.3
	E. Natural Language	0.916	0.515	0.903	0.656
Llama3 (8b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.155	1.0	0.155	0.269
	Natural Language	0.155	1.0	0.155	0.269
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.155	1.0	0.155	0.269
	E. Natural Language	0.596	1.0	0.278	0.435
Mistral (7b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.227	1.0	0.167	0.286
	Natural Language	0.865	0.945	0.537	0.684
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.718	0.957	0.351	0.513
	E. Natural Language	0.954	0.883	0.832	0.857
Mixtral (47b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.244	0.994	0.17	0.29
	Natural Language	0.811	0.975	0.45	0.616
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.948	0.675	0.982	0.8
	E. Natural Language	0.925	0.515	1.0	0.68

Table 2: Individual results of ExactLearner+LLM on the Generations ontology. All the results have been analysed with the Chi-Squared test. The null hypothesis is that there is no correlation between the ontology in constructed by ExactLearner+LLM and the Generations ontology. All of them have p-value lower than 0.05 (i.e., the null hypothesis is always refused).

Model	Prompt & Query	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-Score
Llama2 (13b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.324	0.851	0.178	0.294
	Natural Language	0.853	0.483	0.564	0.52
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.352	0.897	0.191	0.314
	E. Natural Language	0.873	0.233	1.0	0.378
Llama3 (8b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.221	0.995	0.175	0.297
	Natural Language	0.547	0.957	0.262	0.411
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.437	0.884	0.212	0.342
	E. Natural Language	0.889	0.765	0.637	0.695
Mistral (7b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.86	0.517	0.59	0.551
	Natural Language	0.908	0.771	0.701	0.734
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.901	0.518	0.819	0.634
	E. Natural Language	0.933	0.675	0.894	0.769
Mixtral (47b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.341	0.935	0.193	0.32
	Natural Language	0.866	0.569	0.601	0.584
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.876	0.249	1.0	0.399
	E. Natural Language	0.873	0.233	1.0	0.378

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Figure 1: Ablation Study: blue means with simplification and splitting and green means without these operations. Red and yellow correspond to the two operations: simplification and splitting, resp. These are F1-scores aggregated for the small ontologies of the ExactLearner benchmark.

Table 3: Individual results of ExactLearner+LLM on the University ontology. All the results have been analysed with the Chi-Squared test. The null hypothesis is that there is no correlation between the ontology constructed by the ExactLearner+LLM and the University ontology. A yellow line means that the p-value is greater than 0.05 (i.e., the null hypothesis cannot be refused). The red line means that no axiom has been learnt (i.e., empty ontology).

Model	Prompt & Query	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1-Score
Llama2 (13b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.41	1.0	0.116	0.207
	Natural Language	0.896	0.412	0.35	0.378
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.379	0.794	0.092	0.165
	E. Natural Language	-	-	-	-
Llama3 (8b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.41	1.0	0.116	0.207
	Natural Language	0.723	0.971	0.214	0.351
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.175	0.912	0.079	0.146
	E. Natural Language	0.868	0.735	0.338	0.463
Mistral (7b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.61	0.559	0.108	0.181
	Natural Language	0.905	0.824	0.438	0.571
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.667	0.382	0.094	0.15
	E. Natural Language	0.957	0.441	1.0	0.612
Mixtral (47b)	M. OWL Syntax	0.175	0.912	0.079	0.146
	Natural Language	0.95	0.676	0.676	0.676
	E. M. OWL Syntax	0.898	0.265	0.31	0.286
	E. Natural Language	0.937	0.176	1.0	0.3

C Ablation Study: Simplification and Splitting

In Figure 1, we present the F1-scores for different combinations of LLMs and prompts, aggregated for the small ontologies of the ExactLearner benchmark. Recall that the simplification operation omits implied concept names and splitting separates one concept inclusion with multiple conjunctions on the right-hand side into multiple concept inclusions with one conjunct on the right-hand side.

D Galen Modules

Figures 2 and 3 present the distribution of the modules of the GALEN ontology by number of concept and role names.

References

- [1] M. R. C. Duarte, B. Konev, and A. Ozaki. Exactlearner: A tool for exact learning of EL ontologies. In M. Thielscher, F. Toni, and F. Wolter, editors, *KR*, pages 409–414. AAAI Press, 2018. URL <https://aaai.org/ocs/index.php/KR/KR18/paper/view/18006>.

Figure 2: Distribution of of modules in the GALEN ontology by number of concept names.

Figure 3: Distribution of of modules in the GALEN ontology by number of role names.